

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

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Executive Summary

The MICS project follows a bottom-up approach to measure citizen science's effectiveness. It will provide recommendations to help Europe integrate citizen science in policy tools that increase environmental actions' legitimacy and effectiveness.

Nature-based solutions (NBSs) characterise the piloting phase of the project, taking on the challenges of seven *sustainable development goals* (SDGs): the project will provide conceptualisation, implementation, evaluation, and, eventually, proof of the applicability and flexibility of citizen science in the whole cycle of NBS-related research.

Among the SDGs, the “target populations’ good health and well-being” (goal 3), “quality education” (goal 4), “clean water” (goal 6), “sustainable cities and communities” (goal 11), “responsible consumption and production” (goal 12), “life on land” (goal 15) and “strong institutions” (goal 16) are the foundation of the implications of citizen science on NBS science, and therefore provide the context to measure its effectiveness, also in terms of the following MoRRI indicators: SLSE4, PE1, PE2, PE3, PE5, PE6, PE7, PE8, PE9, PE10, OA1, OA2, OA3, OA6, E1 and GOV1.

The SDGs provide an opportunity to standardise citizen-science contributions (both positive and negative) to sustainable development.

The MICS project is developing a set of recommendations and guidelines about indicators oriented to the SDGs that will allow stakeholders to: compare and aggregate data; harmonise data requirements for reporting; and consolidate reporting to other stakeholders.

This short deliverable describes how, in the MICS project, curators (reviewers) have been assigned to oversee the results according to specific SDGs. These curators can also act as moderators in discussion in social media. Curators include experts from the MICS partners and the supporter community outside the consortium. Incentives are provided for them in WP5.

1 Introduction

The main idea in MICS is that, to know if citizen science can contribute to more-responsible research and innovation better than traditional methods, it is necessary to study the empirical evidence about the impact of citizen science on science itself and society. In the domain of the case-study sites, i.e. the science of nature-based solutions, the project involves a broad public in its research, observation, data collection, data aggregation, data analysis and creation of recommendations. MICS initially engaged citizen scientists to identify specific issues and challenges keeping NBS science from being effective in their respective regions by allowing them to submit their views in in-person meetings and online. These views will be cross-checked with the existing literature and other observations stemming from the same area and taken into account in all further activities. Citizens are involved in all project stages, either as part of the consortium, external observers or online contributors. The Forum section of the EU-Citizen.Science platform [<https://eu-citizen.science/forum/>], part of the sister project EU-Citizen.Science and linked to MICS, serves as an online platform for all stakeholders in the project, for exchanging ideas, applying to project's events, and disseminating events, media and results. MICS will use the EU-Citizen.Science platform's discussion forum to: (1) describe, represent and discuss on the impact of citizen science in various languages; (2) debate on the validation of outcomes via automatic procedures (e.g., filtering out irrelevant documents through the training of machine-learning algorithms); (3) discuss on the annotation of data; (4) participate in open peer-review; (5) select

appropriate data to be included in a knowledge repository; (6) evaluate citizen-science procedures at large.

MICS's second period will be focused on developing open, peer-review practices for the NBS science, taking into account the specific technical, practical and ethical aspects of MICS research. "Open, peer-review" is an umbrella term for a broad continuum of practices. In this respect, MICS will systematically build upon insights gained in other EU projects, including EU-Citizen.Science. Scoping will be conducted to gauge researcher attitudes towards open review to determine the optimal peer review system. The first round of open consultations of the NBS science recommendations formulated (which will be translated into the main project languages) has been carried out. Additional consultations will be carried out by addressing relevant stakeholders (policy makers, civil society organisations, NGOs, representatives of academia and media) through the EU-Citizen.Science platform. Additionally, recommendations will be discussed during workshops that will take place in the EU, in the countries of the validation sites.

These tools will support policy making, allowing for stakeholders' efficient engagement thanks to using participatory brainstorming techniques, social networks, and open-data platforms. Further rounds of open consultations of the updated version of NBS science recommendations (again translated into the main project languages) will be carried out.

2 Provision of moderators and curators (reviewers) around SDGs

Curators and moderators have been selected to provide support and guidance for the MICS project. The curators and moderators are experts in citizen science, NBSs or impact assessment. Curators and moderators are also outside of the MICS consortium; therefore, they provide also an external perspective on MICS work. Selecting curators is generally organic, arising from communications with different organisations and people outside of the MICS project.

For example, the River Restoration Centre is a not-for-profit organisation funded by the membership of governmental and non-governmental organisations, trusts and individual members interested in improving the water environment through citizen science and NBSs. Through this network, the River Restoration Centre has developed connections and selected curators and reviewers. For example, in creating a series of policy briefs on NBS Science, 2-page summary briefs aimed at policy-makers, to help with the development, the project has recruited advisors who have many years of experience (guidance, publications, policy briefs, science briefs) in their previous role as Policy Adviser for the England Environment Agency Conservation Policy.

The MICS consortium has also recruited curators and moderators of the project's work through its citizen-science connections. For example, to recruit external reviewers for NBSs related to the SDGs, a message was sent to the *European Citizen Science Association* (ECSA) community (email included below), in November 2020:

Dear all,

As you know, Earthwatch is coordinating the MICS project to measure the impact of citizen science [mics.tools]. We are developing a platform to understand (and quantify) if citizen science benefits the environment, science, governance, society and the economy. MICS also aims to improve the effectiveness of nature-based solutions through test-site development and citizen-science tool validation.

This December, we are submitting a report on Citizen Science and Nature-Based Solutions. The report aims to produce a series of briefs providing recommendations for citizen science activities around nature-based solutions and the integration with policy for different European regions.

We would appreciate your feedback as external reviewers to maximise the benefit of this report for the community, practitioners and policy makers. As a benefit for you, you would have early access to the report, which might be of special interest if you are working on NBSs. You can also decide to get involved in a publication that we plan to produce based on this report.

If you are interested and available to act as a reviewer, please get in touch.

There were eight responses from interested scientists and practitioners in the field of citizen science and NBSs.

3 Conclusions

An open community, formed between the consortium and associated organisations spanning over stakeholders from academia, the private sector, the third sector, and citizen scientists, is conducting citizen-science pilots in four case-study sites. This community covers Western Europe, Southern Europe, and Central and Eastern Europe. A core supporting community has been already set up. WP4 has organised the establishment and engagement of this community. Grassroots movements and associations are playing an essential role in citizens' engagement in the case-study sites. The research process has been opened up to these communities, which actively contribute to the research process. Ideas in each case-study site have been harvested by citizen experiential engagement (WP4), and the project has been developed and conducted by involving local communities. The consortium provides citizen-science expertise; the local communities offer fresh ideas, new perspectives, and additional stakeholders' vision. The case-study sites are demonstrating how citizen science can produce solutions and scientific evidence for a more robust and legitimate NBS science. The methods and instrument developed, tested and validated will constitute a conceptual framework for citizen-science research in general. Science requires the integrity of processes and data; accordingly, future actions in citizen science have to be based on responsibly-gathered data. MICS is providing: (1) a toolbox for measuring impact assessment open to all; (2) free access throughout the project to its peer-reviewed scientific publications; and (3) open access to its results. Furthermore, constant feedback and evaluation inherent to citizen science allowed the consortium to identify optimum methodologies throughout the project, especially during the piloting phase. Citizen-science methods are therefore firmly embedded in the research design when producing recommendations for the future of NBS science and prospective utilisation of citizen-science models in EU-funded projects.